

ANALYSIS OF GENE EXPRESSION PROFILE CHANGES FOLLOWING THERAPY WITH 4-[(3-ETHOXY-3-OXOPROpanOYL) AMINO] BENZOIC ACID IN EXPERIMENTAL CHRONIC HEART FAILURE

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Topicality. Chronic heart failure (CHF) is associated with systemic oxidative stress and significant impairment of cellular metabolism, contributing to damage to target organs, particularly the kidneys. Current therapeutic approaches have limited efficacy in correcting these metabolic disorders. Succinate dehydrogenase (SDH) inhibitors, such as 4-[(3-ethoxy-3-oxopropanoyl) amino] benzoic acid (etmaben), are considered potential agents for metabolic therapy; however, their molecular mechanisms of action in established CHF remain poorly understood.

Aim. To evaluate the effect of 4-[(3-ethoxy-3-oxopropanoyl) amino] benzoic acid on the expression of key genes regulating antioxidant defense, energy metabolism, and cellular homeostasis in the kidney tissue of rats with experimental chronic heart failure.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted on 30 outbred male rats divided into groups: intact control, rats with a CHF model induced by left coronary artery ligation, and CHF rats treated with etmaben from day 30 to day 61 after surgery. The mRNA levels of the genes Nrf2, Gpx1, Cpt1b, Hes1, mTOR, Nox1, and Txnrd1 were assessed in kidney homogenates using real-time polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR). Statistical significance of differences was determined using Student's t-test or one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's post-hoc test.

Results. CHF was found to lead to a significant activation of the transcription factor Nrf2; however, the expression of its target gene, GPx1, was unchanged in both CHF and etmaben-treated groups, indicating dysfunction of this pathway. Therapy with 4-[(3-ethoxy-3-oxopropanoyl) amino] benzoic acid caused a statistically significant increase in the expression of the Cpt1b gene ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a shift in cellular metabolism towards fatty acid β -oxidation. A significant suppression of the pro-oxidant enzyme Nox1 and activation of the thioredoxin reductase 1 (Txnrd1) gene ($p < 0.05$) were also revealed in the treatment groups. The Notch signaling pathway was activated under the influence of etmaben, as evidenced by increased Hes1 gene expression ($p < 0.05$), while no statistically significant effect on mTOR gene expression was observed.

Conclusions. Administration of etmaben against the background of established CHF does not restore the function of the Nrf2/GPx1 pathway, which may be associated with the blockade of target gene transcription induced by succinate accumulation. The mechanism of action of 4-[(3-ethoxy-3-oxopropanoyl) amino] benzoic acid under conditions of experimental CHF can be characterized as metabolic modulation promoting cellular stabilization under chronic stress.